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<https://rebone.eu/>

ReBOne: a Marie Curie Doctoral Network

- Objective:** REBONE aims to establish a multidisciplinary PhD programme focused on advancing the clinical use of bioactive ceramic implants for treating bone defects.
- Main Goal:** To develop a comprehensive design workflow using computational tools to help clinical professionals create personalised bone graft substitutes for critical-size bone defects.
- Key Innovation Aspects:**
- Mechanical and mechano-biological performance optimization.
 - Surgical implantability improvement.
 - Manufacturing process reliability enhancement

Surgical plan in mixed reality environment for bone realignment and fracture reduction from segmentation of bone CT scans.